

Role of Higher Educational Institution in Entrepreneurship Development

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Abstract

Entrepreneurship is set of activities undertaken by an individual in order to acquire together a variety of resources and ideas and merge them to process a commercially acceptable product. To be a victorious entrepreneur, it is very significant to have managerial skill and strong team building abilities. Entrepreneurship development is the process of getting better the skills and knowledge of entrepreneurs all over various training and classroom programs. Entrepreneurship education is definite in broad terms as the building of knowledge and skills for the idea of entrepreneurship generally, as element of predictable education programs at primary, secondary or tertiary-level educational institutions. In the 90s, the country saw the prospective of entrepreneurship not only as an entry-level employment originator, but also as a means of wealth creation. Success stories, particularly in the IT sector, were viewed by entrepreneurs as role models. Key areas of entrepreneurship education could be specified as follows: (a) embedding entrepreneurship into education and training; (b) curriculum development; (c) teacher development; and (d) engagement with the private sector. Despite the tremendous growth in entrepreneurship education, several challenges remain. In today's atmosphere for developing countries especially, funding and compatibility with education, technology and innovation policies may be vital challenges. More effective activity and analysis of the long-run impact of entrepreneurship education programmes on economic process and job creation is required. These should be supported a broadly outlined set of outcomes, not solely on slim measures such as the amount of start-ups created.

Keywords: Entrepreneur, Entrepreneurship, Higher Education, Development

Introduction

Entrepreneurship is set of activities undertaken by an individual in order to carry together a variety of resources and ideas and merge them to process a commercially adequate product. In easy words entrepreneurship is the process of altering ones idea into a successful business venture. To be a winning entrepreneur, it is very important to have managerial skill and tough team building abilities. Leadership attributes are a sign of winning entrepreneurs. Some political economists regard leadership, management ability, and team building skills to be the important qualities of an entrepreneur. Entrepreneurship development is the process of getting better skills and knowledge of entrepreneurs through a variety of training and classroom programs. The complete point of entrepreneurship development is to augment the number of entrepreneurs. By doing

this, the pace at which novel businesses or ventures are finished gets better. This makes room for employment and improves the economy of the country. Nearly 60 per cent Indians have strong entrepreneurial qualities like cheerfulness, business-mindedness, and persistence. But the minority start new businesses. The recent study found that only about 22 per cent of aspiring entrepreneurs have the sufficient access to training. Another study found that more than 80 per cent of the students in the developed nations study at least a skill or a trade earlier than they turn 14 years of age. But, it was only 4 per cent in India.

Growth of Higher Education Institutions in India

During the period of Independence only 20 Universities and 500 colleges with only one lakh students were enrolled in India. At present Higher education in India is one of the largest education systems in India with 378 universities, 18,064 colleges, 4.92 lakhs faculties and 1.4 crores of students in 2007. But our Gross enrolment ratio is low when compared to other developed nations. Out of the total higher educational institutions in India, Private sector has contributed nearly 63.2% in 2007. The share of enrolment has increased from 32.9% to 51.5% during the same period. Private sector has improved access in various areas like engineering, medicine, management studies etc.

The Eleventh Plan estimates to increase the enrolment target for higher education will come from private providers.

Table 1 Growth of Higher Education Institutions

S.No.	Type of Institution	2005-2006		2009-2010	
		Number	% of Total	Number	% of Total
1.	General Education	12,751	65.7	13,381	57.93
2.	Professional Education	5,179	26.7	6,936	30.03
3.	Other Institutions	1,473	7.6	2,782	12.04
	Total	19,403	100.0	23099	100.00

Source: 1. UGC, 2007

2. Statistics of Higher & Technical Education 2009-10

Table 1 shows the number of educational institution and its share in the overall institutions in various sectors like General education, professional education, and other institutions during the period of 2005-06. And the number of institutions and its percentage level during the period of 2009-10.

Figure 1: Number of Educational Institutions in India during the period of 2005 -06 and 2009 -10

The Entrepreneurship Education Ecosystem

Entrepreneurship at rest has a long way to go in terms of earning the status of a referred course amongst management students in India. Perhaps, this status acts as reason enough to only offer entrepreneurship as an extra-curricular or co-curricular program in the middle-of-the-road of the colleges and universities in India. Shankar (2012) classify six primary obstacle to teaching entrepreneurship in India as:

1. Lack of institutionalization
2. Lack of indigenous experience
3. Lack of trained teachers
4. Short-term focus on results
5. Limitations with teaching
6. Subject not considered as core

Evolution of Entrepreneurship Education in India

According to A Global Perspective on Entrepreneurship Education and Training Report 2008, Entrepreneurship education is defined in broad terms as the building of knowledge and skills for the purpose of entrepreneurship generally, as part of recognized education programs at primary, secondary or tertiary-level educational institutions.

Entrepreneurship education in post-independence India has been focused on measures designed to encourage self-employment and founding of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs). The Industrial Policy Resolution of 1956 has, for instance, a very strong emphasis on the SME sector. As the economy transitioned from being primarily agrarian into one that has significant contribution from other sectors, it was felt that the most pressing requirement was education that would enable need based entrepreneurs to make forays into these emerging sectors. Consequently, in the 1960s and 70s, entrepreneurship education was almost exclusively delivered in the form of training programs, offered by institutions under the aegis of State and Central Governments, and by financial institutions receiving support from the Government. Some of the institutions delivering such programs were:

- Industrial estates and in common service facilities (like tool rooms)
- Training and counselling institutions (NISIET, SISI, TCOs, EDI)
- Financial institutions like SBI, IDBI, TDICI, RCTC, etc.
- Development boards (Science and Technology Parks, EDCs, TBIs)

In the 1980s, entrepreneurship education continued to focus primarily on entrepreneur training aimed at creating self-employment ventures. The 80s also saw the entry of entrepreneurship education into technology and management institutions. At the IIM Ahmadabad, for example, faculty members started offering Achievement Motivation Training. Other management institutions also began offering similar courses, driven mainly by faculty interest. However, none of these institutions took on a pioneering role to emerge as a thought-leader. Governmental effort oversaw the founding of an initiative to set up Science and Technology Parks (STEPS) and incubation centers at a few reputed technical institutions. With the advent of liberalization in the 90s, the country saw the potential of entrepreneurship not only as an entry-level employment generator, but also as a means of wealth creation. Success stories, especially in the IT sector, were viewed by entrepreneurs as role models. The country as a whole saw a growing interest in entrepreneurship, fuelled by factors such as growth potential of economy, changing social and cultural environment.

Trends in Entrepreneurship Education

It is important to note the research and educational developments that have occurred over the

past few years. The major themes that characterize recent research about entrepreneurs and new-venture creation can be summarized as follows:

- Intrapreneurship (that is, entrepreneurship within large organizations) and the need for entrepreneurial cultures have gained much attention during the past few years
- Venture financing, gained importance in the 1990s with unique strength, fuelling another decade of entrepreneurship.
- Women and minority entrepreneurs have emerged in unmatched numbers. They appear to face hurdles and barriers different from those that of others.
- Entrepreneurship education is one of the newest topics in B - schools. The number of institutions teaching course has grown from as few as two dozen 20 years ago to more than 500 at this time.

Role of Higher Education Institution in Developing Entrepreneurship In India

- The B schools are the most appropriate nursery of shaping and developing management graduates for entrepreneurship who possess integrity and ethical standards, a deep sense of social responsibility, a commitment to the up- liftment of their communities.
- B Schools are in a position to develop case studies in entrepreneurship practices relevant in the Indian context.
- To promote and develop entrepreneurship education some B-school are starting entrepreneurship education in their course structure.
- Most of them provide the electives in their course structure by which students will give their interest in that field and open their enterprise.
- Courses in entrepreneurship are the core activity of Entrepreneurship education in India.

Challenges in Entrepreneurial Education

- Cultural barriers:- Entrepreneurship can develop only in a society in which cultural norms permit variability in the choice of paths of life. Unfortunately, the Indian culture consists of a network of benefits that in many ways run counter to entrepreneurship (Leo Paul Dana, 2000). People in India are more sensitive to emotional affinity in the workplace than to work and productivity.
- Difficulties towards Start-ups:- Starting a business in India is costly in terms of the time required and the cost involved. While it takes just five days to start a business in the United States and just two days in Australia, in India it takes as long as 89 days.
- Incomplete Entrepreneurship Education:- A survey done by the Entrepreneurship Development Institute, India (EDII) in 2003 shows that young people are afraid to start their own business because they are not confident, not capable, and lack knowledge in starting a business. Many people have the opportunity to change jobs or become an entrepreneur if they are properly trained. The students in India are not satisfied with the “hands-on” support of their university in the founding process.
- Dependence on government:- Degree of dependence on government is another challenge before entrepreneurship education in India. Insufficient private sector participation and lack of sustainable business models in the entrepreneurship education act as barriers to its development in India.

Suggestions to Improve Entrepreneurship Through Higher Education

Key areas of entrepreneurship education could be specified as follows: (a) embedding entrepreneurship into education and training; (b) curriculum development; (c) teacher development; and (d) engagement with the private sector.

A) Embedding Entrepreneurship Into Formal Education and Training

Imparting entrepreneurship into the existing formal educational system at all stages needs a strong commitment both from government and educational institutions in terms of policies and resources. It is good to expose students to business and entrepreneurship. Create perceptions and attitudes about entrepreneurship at early age of students reaching secondary schools. Entrepreneurial education should be incorporated into the curriculum, rather than being offered as standalone courses. At the secondary school level, awareness campaigns and extracurricular activities created to assist students has to be carried out to understand the world of work, which includes business visits. At higher education level, attending elective and/or compulsory courses on entrepreneurship, and participating in more focused activities and projects, has proven particularly effective. Within the university context, entrepreneurship centres can play a key role in catalysing entrepreneurship education both within and outside of the curriculum.

B) Curriculum Development

Entrepreneurship programmes ought to be formed over disciplines, not only over benefits of the business schools alternately monetary divisions. For higher education, a large portion of the procurement for entrepreneurship instruction may be focused once benefits of the business schools or trading and lending departments, which would progressively advertising specializations furthermore actually degrees for entrepreneurship. Same time this might appear to be a common spot to start, confirmation need indicated that the dominant part from claiming business people don't originate from benefits of the business schools at from science, building what's more engineering organization schools. For fact, entrepreneurship could be previously, at whatever discipline alternately division – from medicine, of the arts, will general population administration.

This makes it basic that entrepreneurship a chance to be taught over a cross-disciplinary. Way also not restricted best should business What's more commercial concerns. For creating countries, exactly about. Those zones that ought to further bolstering make incorporated for entrepreneurship curriculums, relying upon the. Instructive level, include: fundamental aptitudes (financial ability and so on.), good fortune recognition,. Business planning, start-up, dealing with the SME, overseeing the move starting with need to. Growth firms, what is more exit/transition of ownership, especially family-owned. The more youthful the target audience, the All the more those educational module needs with a chance to be centered ahead essential aptitudes Furthermore awareness rising. Regarding benefits of the business and entrepreneurship. Viable entrepreneurship training. Programmes concentrate on creating entrepreneurial attitudes, abilities Also practices. This incorporates fabricating self-confidence, self-efficacy, and also heading skills, especially in the grade of more auxiliary levels.

C) Teacher Development

Teachers are the most important key factor in entrepreneurship education. Strategies and ideas will not have any impact without effective teachers to develop the necessary interest and interpreting among students. There is a necessity to extend the amount of entrepreneurship educators, and to additional develop them by providing coaching, notably in interactive teaching ways. Networks and also the sharing of best practices among educators are crucial, too. To date, most of the teacher coaching initiatives and networks developed are at the higher education level. a lot of has to be done at the first and secondary levels, by providing entrepreneurship coaching in teacher coaching institutes. Entrepreneurship education ought to be terribly closely joined with follow. Lecturers ought to be inspired to reach bent on the profession and to integrate it into the training methods.

D) Partnership with the Private Sector

One of the key success factors for entrepreneurship education is that the effective engagement of the non-public sector in facilitating entrepreneurship. This includes business and private academic institutions. Additionally, it suggests that developing networks across sectors to spur partnerships and build associate atmosphere of trust and cooperation within the native scheme and beyond. Private entrepreneurship centres and foundations additionally play a crucial role, each in funding and in serving as centres of experience on entrepreneurship. It is additionally vital to focus on the role of enormous domestic and foreign companies in business development. Large companies are progressively concentrating on their core operations and outsourcing those during which they are doing not have a competitive advantage. Thus, they have a strategic interest in developing the competences of native suppliers, and often take part in cost-sharing in native skills development and upgrading programmes.

Conclusion

Despite the tremendous growth in entrepreneurship education, several challenges remain. One of the predominant challenges is to vary the culture and attitude in countries and regions in which business and entrepreneurship are either not viewed favourably and are not understood. The low level of exposure to business and entrepreneurship, combined with the lack of role models, appears to be making the shift from necessity to opportunity entrepreneurship in several developing countries troublesome. In today’s atmosphere for developing countries especially, funding and compatibility with education, technology and innovation policies may be vital challenges. More effective activity and analysis of the long-run impact of entrepreneurship education programmes on economic process and job creation is required. These should be supported a broadly outlined set of outcomes, not solely on slim measures such as the amount of start-ups created.

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